

Ferroelectricity Induced by Oxygen Vacancies in Rhombohedral ZrO₂ Thin Films

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Rhombohedral phase Hf_xZr_{1-x}O₂ (HZO, x from 0 to 1) films are promising for achieving robust ferroelectric polarization without the need for an initial wake-up pre-cycling, as is normally the case for the more commonly studied orthorhombic phase. However, a large spontaneous polarization observed in rhombohedral films is not fully understood, and there are also large discrepancies between experimental and theoretical predictions. In this work, in rhombohedral ZrO₂ thin films, we show that oxygen vacancies are not only a key factor for stabilizing the phase, but they are also a source of ferroelectric polarization in the films. This is shown experimentally through the investigation of the structural properties, chemical composition and the ferroelectric properties of the films before and after an annealing at moderate temperature (400 °C) in an oxygen environment to reduce the V_O concentration compared. The experimental work is supported by density functional theory (DFT) calculations which show that the rhombohedral phase is the most stable one in highly oxygen defective ZrO₂ films. The DFT calculations also show that V_O contribute to the ferroelectric polarization. Our findings reveal the importance of V_O for stabilizing rhombohedral ZrO₂ thin films with superior ferroelectric properties.

1. Introduction

Defect engineering has been shown to be a versatile approach to further develop ferroelectric thin films for a range of applications.^[1–4] For instance, the electromechanical response of ferroelectric BaTiO₃ thin

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films was demonstrated to be improved by the presence of oxygen vacancies (V_O).^[3] Moreover, increasing the concentration of intrinsic point defects (e.g., lead, titanium, and/or V_O, etc.) has been proven to enhance the energy storage performance of 0.68Pb(Mg_{1/3}Nb_{2/3})O₃-0.32PbTiO₃ (PMN-PT) thin films.^[1] Even more interestingly, ferroelectric and ferroelastic domain walls constitute a new 2D topological defect with exciting functionalities that could play a key role in the transition from nanoscale to atomic-scale electronics.^[5]

Since 2011,^[6] the orthorhombic phase (o-phase) Hf_xZr_{1-x}O₂ (HZO), with x ranging from 0 up to 1, thin films have attracted tremendous attention due to their emergent ferroelectric properties at the nanoscale.^[7–10] These oxides are compatible with the present complementary metal oxide semiconductor (CMOS) technologies, while also being capable of providing robust ferroelectric polarization.^[11,12] Thus they have been extensively considered for ferroelectric memory and field-effect transistors, as well as energy harvesting and storage devices and

sensors.^[13–18] However, the presence of V_O is usually associated with wake-up, where a pre-cycling is usually required to induce a ferroelectric behavior. This is problematic for integrating these materials into reliable memory technologies.^[19] Therefore, defect engineering (particularly reduction/elimination of V_O in the films)^[2,20] is one of the strategies used for achieving wake-up free HZO-based thin films.

In 2018, Wei et al.^[21] demonstrated a novel, wake-up free ferroelectric rhombohedral phase (r-phase) in Hf_{0.5}Zr_{0.5}O₂ films. Later this phase was observed also in ZrO₂ films by Silva et al.^[22] The existence of a large ferroelectric polarization in these materials is not fully understood yet since the theoretical models, based on strain engineering, only predict the existence of a moderate ferroelectric polarization in the films.^[21,22] More recently, by direct oxygen imaging upon undertaking oxygen voltammetry, it was experimentally demonstrated that V_O are key for the stabilization of the rhombohedral phase in Hf_{0.5}Zr_{0.5}O₂,^[23] suggesting that V_O engineering could be a powerful tool towards designing new phases and functionalities in Hf_{0.5}Zr_{0.5}O₂ thin films. In addition, charged V_O were demonstrated theoretically to be responsible for the stabilization of rhombohedral Hf_{0.5}Zr_{0.5}O₂ films on ZnO substrates.^[24,25]

Although r-phase Hf_{0.5}Zr_{0.5}O₂ films show the largest polarization effects, ZrO₂ is much more abundant in nature (by a factor of around 50)^[26] making it a cheaper material to obtain and process, thereby making it a much more attractive choice for large-scale use. Given that,

Boutaybi et al.^[27] applied the model of Materlik^[28] to the r-phase of ZrO₂, showing that the low surface energy might explain the stability of this phase. They found a very small compressive strain (1%) in thin films, and further demonstrated that the r-phase is stable for ZrO₂ thicknesses up to as high as 35 nm. However, they did not provide any explanation about the origin of the ferroelectric polarization in the films. Moreover, to the best of our knowledge, there are no studies about the role of V_O in the ferroelectric polarization of r-phase ZrO₂, or even HZO thin films, while for pure o-phase HfO₂ films a determinant role of the presence of V_O for achieving polarization has been theoretically proposed.^[29]

In this work, we first provide experimental evidence of the presence of V_O in r-phase thin films of ZrO₂, showing the influence of V_O on the ferroelectric response. Next, using density functional theory (DFT) calculations we assess the individual influences of V_O (neutral or charged) and epitaxial strain on the spontaneous polarization and the stability of the r-phase of ZrO₂.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Experimental Evidence of the Role of Oxygen Vacancies on Rhombohedral ZrO₂ Thin Film Polarization

Figure 1a shows a high-resolution cross-sectional TEM image of the ZrO₂ films grown on (111) Nb:SrTiO₃ (Nb:STO) substrates, revealing a

Figure 1. a) HRTEM image showing a crystallite in the ZrO₂ thin films, with the [111] and [11-1] directions marked. The 68.8° angle between the [111] and [11-1] directions is indicative of a rhombohedral (r) structure in the films. b) FFT pattern corresponding to micrograph a). c) Fourier-filtered micrograph of a r-phase ZrO₂ crystallite Fourier filtered micrograph in b) obtained with the (11-1) ZrO₂ and (110)STO spots in the FFT diagram b); the numbers indicate the number of planes in the film (6,7) continued into the substrate (7,8) between the cores of successive mismatch dislocations (endings of the supplementary half-planes in ZrO₂) showing domains of epitaxial growth with a variable lateral size. d) XRD analysis performed on the r-phase ZrO₂ films, performed before and after annealing in an oxygen-rich atmosphere. The blue and pink dashed lines indicate the peaks associated to the m- and o-phases, respectively.

crystalline ZrO₂ layer and a sharp interface between the 8-nm thick ZrO₂ layer and the Nb:STO substrate. The high crystallinity quality as well as the existence of the r-phase in ZrO₂ films were discussed in detail in an earlier study.^[22] In the high resolution TEM image of Figure 2b, a ~68.8° angle was observed between the [111] and [11-1] directions of the imaged grain. The 68.8° angle is indicative of a R3m r-phase. The distance between the (111) planes (d_{111}) of the r-phase ZrO₂ films was measured to be $d_{111} = 2.98 \pm 0.06$ Å, which compares to the bulk theoretical value of 2.94 Å. This corresponds to an estimated out-of-plane tension of ~1.3%, and thus in-plane compression of ~1%.^[22]

In order to describe the thin film-substrate orientation relationship we processed Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) patterns on HRTEM images on (111) ZrO₂ film grown on (111) Nb:STO substrate. In the FFT pattern of Figure 1b a well-defined set of peaks emerged from the zone axis of the oriented ZrO₂ grains and from the (111) Nb:STO substrate. The (110)_{STO} and (11-1)_{ZrO₂} peaks were identified and assigned as indicated in Figure 1b. The angle between the two reciprocal vectors and, correspondingly, between the associated families of planes (111)_{STO} and (11-1)_{ZrO₂}, of Figure 1c, is ~22 degrees. The interplanar distances of the (11-1)_{ZrO₂} planes ($d_{11-1} = 0.294$ nm) and the (110)_{STO} planes ($d_{110} = 0.275$ nm) give a lattice mismatch of around -6.9%, which rules out conventional epitaxy. The epitaxial relationship can be explained via a near coincidence lattice model^[30] or domain matching epitaxy (DME),^[31] with the formation of dislocations as the stress relief mechanism. The image in Figure 1c, obtained with the (11-1)_{ZrO₂} and (110)_{STO} peaks from the FFT diagram, is a Fourier filtered image and shows the formation of the misfit dislocations at the ZrO₂-STO interface with epitaxy domains of variable lateral size. Therefore, r-phase ZrO₂ films can be grown on (111) Nb:STO substrates through DME (See Supporting Information for the determination of domain sizes and mismatch). We note that we examined several regions of the film using HRTEM and found the same features throughout the film. Thus, HRTEM provides representative information about the film structure.

Figure 1d shows the XRD patterns for the ZrO₂ films grown on (111) Nb:STO substrates. Besides the Bragg peak approximately centered at $2\theta = 39.97^\circ$, originating from the (111) planes of the SrTiO₃ substrate, one significant diffraction peak centered at $2\theta = 30.27^\circ$ ($d = 2.95$ Å) is observed, which was previously attributed to the r-phase ZrO₂.^[22]

To investigate the role of V_O on the crystallinity quality and ferroelectric response of the r-phase ZrO₂ films, the films were annealed in an oxygen-rich atmosphere ($p_{O_2} = 10$ mbar) at a moderate temperature (400 °C) for 3 h to oxidize them. Figure 1d also shows the XRD pattern of the film after the annealing process together with the typical peak positions corresponding to the monoclinic and orthorhombic phases, marked with blue and pink colors, respectively.^[22] In spite of the slight change of the r-phase peak shape after annealing, no obvious peak associated with the m-phase is observed after annealing. It was also observed that a small variation in thickness (e.g. 1 nm) could have a strong impact on the XRD (111) peak intensity and shape of HZO and ZrO₂ r-phase films.^[21,27] In our case, it is believed that the change in oxygen vacancy concentration is the cause of the small peak shape variation. Moreover, Supporting Information Figure S1 shows that the ZrO₂ films grown by sputtering at 330 °C and then rapid thermally annealed at 600 °C are still amorphous, hence ruling out the possibility of the formation of any m- or o- phases during the annealing step. This finding is in agreement with Hoffmann et al.^[32] who proposed a model describing the dependence of the film crystallinity on the thermal budget, dopant concentration, and film thickness for doped-HfO₂ films. It was proposed that a high thermal budget is needed to form monoclinic films.

Figure 2. Characterization and annealing of 8 nm ZrO_2 thin films grown on Nb:STO(111) substrates. a) XPS O 1s and b) Zr 2p core-level spectra measured at 70° before and after the annealing process in O_2 at $p\text{O}_2 = 10$ mbar and $T = 400^\circ\text{C}$ for 3 h, followed by slow cooling in the same atmosphere. c) P-V loops for the Nb:STO/ ZrO_2 /Au capacitor before and after annealing. d) I-V curves for the Nb:STO/ ZrO_2 /Au capacitor before and after annealing. e) Schematic representation of the annealing process. Here and in the following green and red spheres represent Zr and O atoms, respectively.

We further evaluated the presence of V_{O} and chemical states in r-phase ZrO_2 films grown on (111) Nb:SrTiO₃ substrates. The best conditions to investigate the r-phase ZrO_2 films by XPS are discussed in Supporting Information (Figure S2). Figure 2a shows the O 1s core-level spectra for the ZrO_2 layer measured at 70° before and after the annealing. The XPS peak assigned to the O 1s peak exhibits several spectral components and the best deconvolution is obtained using three Voigt functions, centered at around 529.5 ± 0.1 , 531.2 ± 0.1 and 532.8 ± 0.1 eV, which were attributed to lattice oxygen (O_{L}), oxygen vacancies (O_{V}), and chemically adsorbed oxygen species (O_{C}), respectively.^[33] It is possible to observe a significant change in the O 1s spectrum after the annealing at 400°C . The O_{C} component in the O 1s peak almost disappeared, which can be explained by the loss of the chemically adsorbed oxygen species in the oxygen environment. In addition, the $\text{O}_{\text{V}}/\text{O}_{\text{L}}$ ratio for the ZrO_2 film is 0.76 and 0.41, before and after the annealing, respectively. This confirms a decrease of V_{O} concentration after annealing. While it is not possible to quantify the O content difference by XPS or any other method, this large change in peak ratios indicates a non-negligible change. In order to better justify the existence of V_{O} observed in the O 1s spectra, we further analyzed the Zr 2p spectra (Figure 2b), showing that there is a 160 mV peak shift towards higher binding energy after annealing in O_2 . This observation further supports our conclusion regarding the reduction of V_{O} concentration, as observed in the O 1s before and after O_2 annealing.^[34,35]

The P-V loops measured for a Nb:STO/ ZrO_2 /Au capacitor before and after annealing are shown in Figure 2c. Before the annealing process, a well-saturated hysteresis loop was obtained, without any wake-up cycling. The comparative values of spontaneous polarization (P_{s}), average remnant polarization (P_{r}), and average coercive field (E_{c}) are as follows:

$$\text{As-produced: } P_{\text{s}} = 20.2 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}, P_{\text{r}} = 10.8 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2} \\ E_{\text{c}} = 1.5 \text{ MV cm}^{-1}.$$

$$\text{After oxidation annealing: } P_{\text{s}} = 7.7 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}, P_{\text{r}} = 6.4 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2} \\ E_{\text{c}} = 2.1 \text{ MV cm}^{-1}.$$

The lower E_{c} of the epitaxial films before annealing with respect to the E_{c} of the same films after annealing in an oxygen environment

could be due to a greater number of V_{O} which could facilitate domain switching, as was observed in epitaxial La-doped HfO_2 films.^[1] From a theoretical point of view, it has also been shown that V_{O} -rich HfO_2 exhibits a smaller energy barrier for dipole switching than oxygen defect-free HfO_2 .^[36] explaining our experimentally observed increase in E_{c} after oxygenation annealing. It has also been shown that topological domain walls and phase boundaries can form when secondary m- or t-phases are present leading to a lower value of E_{c} .^[37] Since we see an increase in E_{c} after annealing, this is indicative of a lack of secondary phase formation.

In order to further investigate the annealing effect, current–voltage (I-V) curves were measured. The I-V characteristics for a Nb:STO/ ZrO_2 /Au capacitor before and after the annealing are shown in Figure 2d. It is clear that the leakage current decreases after annealing. At +4 V, the Nb:STO/ ZrO_2 /Au capacitor before annealing shows a current ≈ 21 times higher than the one observed in the annealed capacitor. Moreover, the rectifying behaviors ($I_{-4\text{V}}/I_{+4\text{V}}$) were calculated for the I-V curves before and after the annealing in an oxygen environment and were found to be 2.6 and 22.6, respectively. The I-V curve become more asymmetric after the annealing because the contribution of V_{O} to the conduction is reduced, and the electrode/film interface becomes more significant. Considering that the electrodes Nb:STO(111) and Au have different work functions of 4.46^[38] and 5.4 eV^[39] respectively, the I-V curve after annealing is more asymmetric. This behavior confirms that the annealing step reduces the defect concentration and subsequently improves the insulating characteristics of the ZrO_2 film.^[2] This result agrees with the XPS analysis of Figure 2a and the P-V loops shown in Figure 2c, which showed a lower V_{O} concentration after the annealing step, as shown schematically in Figure 2e.

The fact that both P_{s} and P_{r} decrease after annealing could be either due to a reduction of strain or a decrease of the V_{O} concentration or both. Although annealing can reduce strain in thin films, this would not be expected here at such a low annealing temperature and short time. Moreover, XRD results did not show any change in the structural properties of the films before and after the annealing. The $\sim 1\%$ in-plane strain estimated in our films would lead to only a negligible polarization, that is, $<1 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ variation in accordance with a polarization strain-driven model.^[22] Therefore, it can be concluded that the decrease of P_{s} and P_{r} with annealing is linked to the reduction of V_{O} and not reduction of strain. Further understanding is provided by theoretical calculations, as shown in the next section.

2.2. DFT Calculations of the Stability of Different Phases in ZrO_2 with Respect to V_{O} and Strain

To unravel the connection between strain, V_{O} and polarization, it is first necessary to thoroughly assess the stability of ZrO_2 phases as a function of both strain and V_{O} . Previous studies suggested a strain-driven model to justify the spontaneous polarization in r-phase films of ZrO_2 , therefore it is crucial to investigate if the material could actually bear such

Figure 3. Density functional theory calculation results for *r*-phase ZrO_2 free-standing (111)-oriented slabs. a) Diagrammatic representation of the *r*-phase ZrO_2 unit cell used to construct the (111)-oriented slabs, where the (111) direction corresponds to the *c* axis. The d_{111} and d_{11-1} distances are highlighted in blue and orange, respectively. The direction of spontaneous polarization P_s is shown as well, in cyan b) Calculated (calc.) d_{111} and d_{11-1} as a function of slab thickness for the *r*-phase. The short dashed lines represent the d_{111} and d_{11-1} values of epitaxially strained bulk with 1% compressive strain. The circle and diamond symbols are measured (exp.) d_{111} and d_{11-1} values taken from Silva et al.^[22] with the longer dashed lines connected the points acting as guides to the eye. c) P_s of the bulk *r*-phase of ZrO_2 , directed along the (111) direction, as a function of equiaxial in-plane compressive strain. d) Surface energies under different equiaxial in-plane compressive strains.

epitaxial compressive strain as to induce a significant out-of-plane polarization. The most common phases in ZrO_2 are considered, that is, orthorhombic $\text{Pca}2_1$ (o), tetragonal $\text{P}4_2/\text{nmc}$ (t), monoclinic $\text{P}2_1/\text{c}$ (m), and rhombohedral $\text{R}3\text{m}$ (r) phases of ZrO_2 . While the m-phase is the one with the lowest bulk formation energy, the o-phase is the only one with an appreciable spontaneous polarization. Those phases are most stable in films with (111) orientation, because the (111) facet has the lowest surface energy. In Supporting Information Figure S3 and Table S1, the stress-free lattice constants, formation energies and spontaneous polarization for all the four phases are shown.

One of the advantages of HfO_2 and ZrO_2 -based thin films is the possibility to achieve a robust ferroelectric polarization in few-nm thick films, which is extremely challenging in conventional perovskite-based ferroelectric films.^[40,41] In fact, it was revealed recently that o-phase ZrO_2 ultrathin films deposited on silica substrate have ferroelectric order down to a film thickness of 5 Å, revealing that ZrO_2 can be very promising for scaled energy-efficient electronics.^[42] Therefore, we have done our study up to a thickness of 3.3 nm (12 layers), which meets the current needs of nanoelectronics. It is worth noting that in relation to thicker films, it was recently shown experimentally that *r*-phase ZrO_2 films are stable up to 35 nm.^[27]

The stabilities of free-standing slabs, used as a system which mimics films of the different phases of ZrO_2 (o, r, t, m) was evaluated by calculating the surface energy of fully relaxed (111)-oriented slabs. A range of slab thicknesses, *n*, with *n* indicating the number of atomic layers in the slab and going from three to six layers was considered. In addition,

slabs with *n* = 9 and *n* = 12 layers were also considered to observe the asymptotic trends for increasingly larger thicknesses. Calculations of the surface energy and in-plane lattice parameters (ILP) for the various ZrO_2 phases as a function of slab thickness are reported in Supporting Information Figure S4.

As shown previously in calculations on HfO_2 ^[43] and ZrO_2 ,^[22] the polarization of the *r*-phase is closely linked to structural properties, i.e. polarization increases with d_{111} , which in turn increases with the equiaxial in-plane compressive strain applied to the film. To verify whether the reduction of film thickness could provide large P_s in the *r*-phase ZrO_2 films, such as in HfO_2 thin films,^[43] we calculated the d_{111} and d_{11-1} values (shown in Figure 3a), for the (111)-oriented *r*-phase films as a function of the slab thickness, and for an ideal *r*-phase bulk at 1% epitaxial compressive strain, that is, the typical strain found in experimental films. As shown in Figure 3b, there is a good agreement between the measured and calculated bulk values for d_{111} and d_{11-1} (open symbols and dashed lines, respectively). Further, an increase of d_{111} at the same time as a decrease of d_{11-1} was observed as the film thickness decreased, thus diverging further from the calculated bulk values, namely 2.98 ± 0.07 Å and 2.92 ± 0.07 Å (dashed lines in Figure 3c). Hence for *n* = 3, corresponding to a thickness of 6.054 Å, d_{111} was calculated to be 3.04 ± 0.04 Å and d_{11-1} was calculated to be 2.86 ± 0.07 Å. The observed trend of d_{111} and d_{11-1} is a consequence

of the fact that the relaxed in-plane lattice parameter (ILP) of the *r*-phase film decrease with the film thickness (Supporting Information Figure S4b), and for the *n* = 3 film a ILP of 6.915 Å was found, corresponding to an in-plane compression of 3.85% when compared to the ILP of bulk *r*-phase.

However, the increase of d_{111} of *r*-phase ZrO_2 (111)-oriented films observed when decreasing the film thickness, with a calculated maximal value of 3.04 ± 0.04 Å for a film thickness of 6.054 Å (and an ILP compression of 3.85%), is not sufficient to provide a large out-of-plane polarization according to the strain-driven model proposed in previous works.^[22] To clarify this, we report in Figure 3c the calculated P_s along the (111) direction of the *r*-phase unit cell as a function of the in-plane equiaxial compressive strain. Our calculations show that large (>4%) in-plane compressive epitaxial strains in films are required for *r*- ZrO_2 films to display a large out-of-plane polarization. We do not have such large in-plane strains in our films and yet still find strong ferroelectricity.

To check the stability of *r*-phase slabs under different in-plane equiaxial compressive strains, as would originate from epitaxial growth, the surface energies of the (111)-oriented *r*-phase slabs were calculated for different film thicknesses and different strains, as shown in Figure 3d. The results clearly show that the applied in-plane strain destabilizes the (111)-oriented *r*-phase films at large thickness. This is particularly evident for 3% in-plane compressive strain. Even for a small compressive strain of 1.5%, a slight positive deviation of the calculated surface energy with respect to that of an unstrained slab at *n* = 12 is

observed. For extreme strains such as 6%, for which a large polarization of $21.08 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ should be observed (Figure 3c), only slabs with $n < 6$ were stable, indicating that only ultrathin films ($< 12.9 \text{ \AA}$, i.e., few unit cells) are stable under large compressive in-plane strain conditions.

All the above results indicate that r-phase films are stable at large thicknesses only when the in-plane compressive stress values are $< 1.5\%$. Furthermore, the relaxed r-phase has the lowest surface energy compared to the other structures of ZrO_2 (Supporting Information Figure S4a) and hence would be the preferred structure to form in films. These predictions agree with earlier experimental findings,^[22,27] which show that r-phase ZrO_2 films are observed under conditions of low compressive in-plane stress (1%). In terms of polarization, this means that epitaxial compressive strain could not solely be responsible for the large observed P_s values in r-phase films. Clearly, if a large compressive strain could be induced in an r-phase ZrO_2 film, it will certainly have a strong impact on P_s .

Considering that the ZrO_2 films on Nb:STO(111) of this work were grown and cooled in the absence of oxygen and that after oxidation annealing the ferroelectric polarization degraded (Figure 2), it is important to confirm the role V_{O} on the relative stabilities of the different ZrO_2 phases. We did this with further DFT calculations below and calculated the formation energies of the different ZrO_2 bulk phases for a range of concentrations of neutral (Figure 4b) and charged (Figure 4c) defects.

First, we note that both neutral (V_{O}^x) and charged (V_{O}^{\bullet}) oxygen vacancy defects can be present in ZrO_2 and HfO_2 .^[44]

As shown in Figure 4a, in the r-phase bulk unit cell there are four inequivalent O atoms. We calculated the formation energies under O-poor conditions of a single V_{O}^x in the r-phase unit cell corresponding to a density of V_{O}^x of 4.16 O at. % as well as in the o-, m-, and t-phase bulks, the cells containing either 2 (o,m) or 1 (t) inequivalent positions for O atoms at the same concentration of V_{O}^x (Figure 4b). In the presence of V_{O}^x , the relative energetic ordering of the phases is the same as for ideal bulk (i.e., at 0% concentration of V_{O}^x). The closeness of the order is greater when comparing bulk r- and t- phases, compared to m- and o-phases. At a high V_{O}^x concentration of 12.5 O at. %, even though the formation energies are close for the different phases, the

bulk m-phase is the most energetically favorable one. For the highest V_{O}^x concentrations, the bulk r-phase is more energetically favorable than the bulk t-phase, but the bulk r-phase is still less stable than the bulk o- and m-phases.

The calculated defect formation energies, are listed in Supporting Information Table S2. It is observed that V_{O}^x in r-phase bulk has a formation energy of 0.626 eV, and that the r-phase is more easily formed than the other phases, especially than the o- and m-phases.

Considering the $1+$ state, V_{O}^{\bullet} , we note that this defect is unlikely to spontaneously form for any value of the Fermi energy (see Supporting Information Figure S5). Hence, we discuss doubly ionized V_{O}^{\bullet} next. Figure 4c shows that for low defect concentrations the relative phase ordering is essentially the same as for defect-free systems. However, as the concentration of V_{O}^{\bullet} increases, the r- and t-phases become progressively more favored, and the r-phase becomes the most stable one at 2.08 O at.%. Conversely, at larger concentrations of V_{O}^{\bullet} the bulk o- and m-phases become less stable in presence of such charged defects. The reason for this might be related to the difference in dielectric constants between these phases, with bulk t- and r-phase having much larger dielectric constants than m- and o-phase ones (Supporting Information Table S1). A larger dielectric constant means a larger screening of defect-defect interactions, whose effects become important at higher concentrations. Overall, using DFT calculations we demonstrated that V_{O}^{\bullet} stabilizes the r-phase of ZrO_2 , eventually making it the most energetically favored one. The results shown in of Figure 4c are confirmed by Supporting Information Figure S5 where we have shown a negative defect formation energy of V_{O}^{\bullet} in the r-phase ZrO_2 under O-poor conditions for a wide range of Fermi energies. Hence V_{O}^{\bullet} can be spontaneously present in the thin film samples fabricated under the low oxygenation conditions of this work.

2.3. Influence of Oxygen Vacancies on Polarization

We recall from the theoretical strain-driven model that an in-plane compression of at least 4% (Figure 4c) was needed to provide a significant polarization buildup.^[22] However, this work and other experimental works show that ferroelectricity is present in r-phase films

Figure 4. a) View along axis a of the r-phase ZrO_2 unit cell. The 4 inequivalent O atoms are labeled. b) Relative formation energies, E_t , of the different structures of ZrO_2 expressed as $E_t^x - E_t^m$, with E_t^x and E_t^m being the formation energies of the x (o, t, r) and m-phases, respectively, in eV per formula unit (fu), as a function of neutral oxygen vacancy (V_{O}^x) concentration. The values are all positive indicating that in presence of V_{O}^x all the x -phases are less energetically favorable when compared to the m-phase. c) The phase formation energy, E_t , expressed in eV per formula unit (fu) of different ZrO_2 phases, as a function of doubly positive charged oxygen vacancy (V_{O}^{\bullet}) concentration.

Figure 5. Calculated atomic displacements, represented by the arrows, for Zr (black arrows) and O (blue arrows) atoms in a ZrO_2 r-phase unit cell, following the creation of a V_O^\times or $\text{V}_\text{O}^{..}$ in the position indicated in the top structure. To make them visible, the same 20 \times magnification factor has been applied to the displacements for both cases.

which have no strain or a only a low level of in-plane compressive strain.^[22,27] Therefore, we can conclude that the observed large spontaneous polarization of (111)-oriented r-phase ZrO_2 is not linked directly to the strain. On the other hand, our experimental and theoretical work shows that doubly charge oxygen vacancies, $\text{V}_\text{O}^{..}$, are critical for achieving strong ferroelectric polarization in these films.

In **Figure 5** we show the displacements of Zr and O atoms induced in a r-phase unit cell by the presence of V_O^\times and $\text{V}_\text{O}^{..}$, which are calculated with respect to the fully relaxed defect-free r-phase unit cell. By comparing the two cases, it is clear that in the $\text{V}_\text{O}^{..}$ case the induced displacements are much larger. Since displacements and polarization are linked by the Born effective charge tensor Z_{ij}^* , defined for each atom as the change in polarization along direction i caused by a displacement along j , it is expected that larger displacement should induce larger polarization, provided that the symmetry of the crystal does not provide cancellation effects of the various contribution to the total P_s .

Table 1. P_s values for the r, t, and m phases at different V_O concentration and charge states. The concentration of 4.16% was obtained by creating one vacancy within a 36-atom cell, while the concentration of 0.51 was obtained by doing the creating one vacancy within a 288-atom cell.

Phase – V_O site	P_s ($\mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$) V_O^\times (4.16 at %)	P_s ($\mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$) V_O^\times (0.51 at %)	P_s ($\mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$) $\text{V}_\text{O}^{..}$ (0.51 at %)
r-O(II)	1.33	0.14	4.08
r-O(IV)	2.20	0.33	3.66
r-O(I)	2.53	0.29	2.26
r-O(III)	0.02	0.02	1.33
t-O(I)	0.54	0.35	0.33
m-O(I)	0.20	0.07	0.47
m-O(II)	0.57	0.07	0.59

To confirm the hypothesized link between V_O concentration and spontaneous polarization P_s , we calculated P_s along the (111) direction of bulk ZrO_2 phases in the presence of both neutral and charged V_O (**Table 1**). We observe that the relaxed defect-free rhombohedral unit cell has a negligible (but non-zero) polarization of $0.011 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$. On the other hand, when non-ionized oxygen vacancies, V_O^\times , are present at a level of 4.16%, P_s increases up to $2.20 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$. Lower polarization levels are induced by V_O^\times in the m- and t- phases. Also, for lower V_O^\times concentration of 0.51 O at. %, the polarization is smaller than for larger V_O^\times concentration, suggesting a correlation between V_O^\times and P_s .

We now consider the influence of the same concentration of doubly ionized oxygen vacancies, $\text{V}_\text{O}^{..}$, that is, 0.51 O at. %, in the r-phase. Polarization values from 1 to $4 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ were found for the different vacancy positions, significantly larger than for the neutral defects at the same concentration. Regarding the other phases, the P_s values found at a $\text{V}_\text{O}^{..}$ concentration of 0.51 O

at. % are $0.33 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ in the t-phase and $0.53 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ in the m-phase (averaged over the two possible $\text{V}_\text{O}^{..}$ sites). These calculations further prove that $\text{V}_\text{O}^{..}$ are critical for achieving ferroelectricity in r-phase ZrO_2 . In addition, we demonstrated that V_O^\times can provide a source of P_s as well, even though their contribution is lower due to the smaller displacements induced on the neighboring atoms by their presence (**Figure 5**).

In order to illustrate the separate roles of V_O ($\text{V}_\text{O}^{..}$ or V_O^\times) and in-plane strain on the magnitude of ferroelectric polarization in r-phase ZrO_2 , in **Figure 6** we schematically show of their influences on ferroelectric polarization. While a high out-of-plane tensile strain has not yet been demonstrated in r-phase ZrO_2 films, if it could be achieved without being induced by a large in-plane epitaxial strain, then it would likely be additive to the V_O effect for enhancing ferroelectricity.

3. Conclusions

In this work, we have shown experimentally, through XPS and ferroelectric loops, that a few percent level of V_O leads to ferroelectric polarization in r-phase of ZrO_2 films. This is achieved by growing films under low oxygenation conditions. The ferroelectricity is degraded once the films are oxidation annealed. DFT calculations revealed that the r-phase is the most stable phase when the films are grown in an O-poor environment. Indeed, the formation energies indicate that charged oxygen vacancies, $\text{V}_\text{O}^{..}$ have a dramatic effect on the relative phase stability, with the r-phase becoming favored over the others as the defect concentration increases. In addition, it is clearly demonstrated that charged $\text{V}_\text{O}^{..}$ in the r-phase of ZrO_2 , as well as, to a lesser extent, neutral V_O , have a positive impact to the observed large spontaneous polarization of this phase. Further work investigating oxygen vacancy defect control in the r-phase of ZrO_2 and also in other group IV oxides will undoubtedly shed new light on ways to achieve wake-up free ferroelectric films for next-generation of memory and neuromorphic devices.

Figure 6. Schematic diagram predicting the influences of V_O concentration (as determined from this work) and compressive in-plane strain (from standard ferroelectric theory), leading to tensile out-of-plane strain on spontaneous polarization, P_s , for rhombohedral-phase ZrO_2 thin films.

4. Methods

Eight-nanometer thick ZrO_2 thin films were deposited on (111) $Nb:SrTiO_3$ (Nb:STO) substrates by ion-beam sputtering deposition technique and rapid thermal annealed as described in Silva et al.^[22] to promote the growth of r-phase films. In order to explore the impact of the V_O concentration on the ferroelectric response of the r-phase ZrO_2 films, the films were first put in vacuum ($\sim 10^{-5}$ mbar) and then annealed in oxygen ($PO_2 = 10$ mbar) at 400 °C for 3 h.

The TEM images of the ZrO_2 films deposited on the $Nb:SrTiO_3$ (111) substrates were obtained on a JEM-ARM 200F analytical electron microscope operated at 200 kV. The details of sample preparation can be found in Silva et al.^[22] For the ferroelectric characterization, circular gold (Au) electrodes (diameter of 1 mm) were deposited by thermal evaporation on the upper surface of the films. The ferroelectric hysteresis loops (P-V) were measured at room temperature with a modified Sawyer–Tower circuit using a sinusoidal signal at 1 kHz.

The thin films were structurally characterized by conventional X-ray diffraction (XRD) with a Bruker D8 Discover diffractometer using $Cu-K\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.54056 \text{ \AA}$).

The XPS measurement was done in a X-ray photoelectron spectrometer (SPESCS Surface Nano Analysis, GmbH), equipped with a monochromatized Al-K α X-ray source and a multichannel electron energy analyzer (Specs Phoibos 150) coupled with a differentially pumped electrostatic pre-lens system. Survey scans were recorded for all the samples along with Zr 3d, O 1s, C 1s, and Sr 3d core-level spectra. The core-level spectra were recorded with pass energy of 20 eV, step size of 0.05 eV, and dwell time of 200 ms. The I-V curves were investigated at room temperature with a Keithley 617 programmable electrometer.

All DFT calculations were performed using the VASP code^[45–47] which implements the projector augmented wave method.^[48] The GGA approximation was used along with the PBESol^[49] functional. Slab calculations have been performed under periodic boundary conditions and with the surface normal oriented along the c-axis. The thickness of the vacuum slab was set to 15 Å to avoid spurious interactions between periodic images.

The plane wave energy cutoff has been set to 600 eV for all calculations, while the size of gamma-centered K-point grids has been adjusted accordingly to the (super)cell sizes: a $6 \times 6 \times 6$ grid has been used for simple unit cells of p, m, and t-phases, a $4 \times 4 \times 3$ for (111)-oriented cells, and a $2 \times 2 \times 2$ for the large supercells used in defect energy calculations. For defect calculations, atomic positions were relaxed and lattice parameters were left constant and equal to those of relaxed bulk. Structural relaxation was carried on until atomic forces reached the threshold value of 0.01 eV \AA^{-1} .

The spontaneous polarization was calculated using the modern theory of polarization, as implemented in VASP.^[50] In each phase, all the inequivalent positions for V_O have been considered.

The surface energy γ have been calculated using the formula:

$$\gamma = 0.5 \cdot (E_{\text{slab}} - nE_{\text{bulk}}) / S, \quad (1)$$

Where S is the slab surface, E_{bulk} is the bulk energy per formula unit of the same phase as the slab, and n indicates the number of formula units in the slab. The factor 0.5 appears because symmetric slabs were always considered. Because of this, dipole moment corrections were relevant only for the Pca2₁ phase, while for all the other phases they were unnecessary. When an equiaxial in-plane compressive strain η is applied, the ILP under strain is always calculated with respect to its fully relaxed bulk unit cell value a_0 , according to the formula:

$$a(\eta) = a_0(1 - \eta), \quad (2)$$

and the same holds for the other lattice parameter b . In this work we report compressive strains as positive. Atomic position and the value of the out-of-plane lattice parameter were relaxed, with thresholds of 0.01 eV \AA^{-1} and 0.1 Gpa for atomistic forces and stress along out-of-plane direction, respectively.

The formation energy E_f of the relevant ZrO_2 phases was calculated as:

$$E_f = \frac{1}{N} \left(E_{\text{tot}} - \sum_i n_i \mu_i \right), \quad (3)$$

Where E_{tot} is the total energy of the system and n_i and μ_i denote the number of atoms and chemical potential of species i , respectively. In particular, we used as chemical potentials for Zr and O the energies per atom in HCP Zr and molecular O_2 , respectively.

The Oxygen vacancy formation energy $E_F^{V_O}(\epsilon_F)$ has been calculated using the formula:

$$E_F^{V_O}(\epsilon_F) = E_{\text{tot}}^{V_O} - \sum_i n_i \mu_i + q(E_{\text{VBM}} + \epsilon_f) + q\Delta V + E_c, \quad (4)$$

Where q is the charge state, $E_{\text{tot}}^{V_O}$ is the total energy of the system containing the defect, E_{VBM} is the valence band maximum (VBM) energy, ϵ_f is the Fermi energy, and ΔV and E_c are correction terms which have been evaluated using the self-consistent potential correction scheme when in presence of charged defects.^[51] These corrections can be applied to orthogonal cells only. To ensure this for the o-phase, a slightly lower defect density was considered. For the same reason, the charge corrections on the m-phase could not be directly calculated and to overcome this we assumed that they were equivalent to that of the o-phase at same defect density. To take into account O-poor conditions, it was assumed that $\mu_{Zr} = \mu_{Zr,HCP}$ and $\mu_O = 0.5(\mu_{ZrO_2} - \mu_{Zr,HCP})$, which is obtained by considering that at equilibrium conditions the relationship $\mu_{ZrO_2} = \mu_{Zr} + 2\mu_O$ holds, with μ_{ZrO_2} being the total energy per formula unit of ZrO_2 .

For charged defects, $2 \times 2 \times 2$, $2 \times 2 \times 1$ and $2 \times 1 \times 1$ supercells of the r-phase ZrO_2 have been employed, with a $2 \times 2 \times 2$, $3 \times 2 \times 3$ and $3 \times 4 \times 3$ Gamma-centered K-point grid, respectively. Since the charge corrections require the dielectric constant, it was calculated using DFT methods. The ionic contribution to the dielectric constant of all phases has been obtained using density functional perturbation theory, while the electronic one has been obtained through the response to a finite electric field.

The various phases were confirmed using the FINDSYM web server.^[52,53] The atomistic representations of the interfaces have been obtained using VESTA.^[54]

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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